

TABLE 1—THIAZOLO [3,2-a] THIENO [3,2-e] PYRIMIDIN 4-ONES (III)

Compound	Thiocyanoketone used	Ar	Yield %	m. p. °C	M. F.	Analytical results	
						Found %	Required %
a	α -Thiocyano acetophenone	H	68	338	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS ₂	C, 62.01 H, 3.93 N, 9.40	61.54 3.85 8.98
b	<i>p</i> -Chloro α -thiocyano acetophenone	Cl	52	> 300	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ OS ₂	C, 55.73 H, 3.42 N, 8.12	55.41 3.17 8.08
c	<i>p</i> -Bromo α -thiocyano acetophenone	Br	53	> 300	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrN ₂ OS ₂	C, 49.43 H, 3.08 N, 7.34	49.11 2.82 7.16
d	<i>p</i> -Methyl α -thiocyano acetophenone	CH ₃	63	> 300	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS ₂	N, 8.62	8.59
e	<i>p</i> -Methoxy α -thioeyano acetophenone	OCH ₃	56	> 300	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	C, 60.00 H, 4.12 N, 8.61	59.65 4.09 8.19

Compounds a, c, d and e were crystallised from ethanol and compound b was crystallised from dioxan.

thyl 2-phenacylthiothieno [2, 3-d] pyrimidine-4(3H)-one with sulphuric acid and arbitrarily assigned one the structure IIIa (m.p. 336-8°) and the other VI (m.p. 228-30°). The present work incidentally shows the assignment to be correct.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in paraffin liquid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were taken on Perkin Elmer grating IR spectrometer 621 in nujol and pmr was recorded on 60 MHz Varian spectrometer in TFA.

2,3-Dimethyl-8-aryl-4H-thiazolo [3, 2-a] thieno [3, 2-e] pyrimidine-4-one(III a-e) :

A solution of α -thiocyanoacetophenone(II, 0.01 mole) in ethanol (10 ml) was mixed with an ethanolic solution of 2-amino-3-carbethoxy-4,5-dimethylthiophene hydrochloride (I, 2.35 g; 0.01 mole in 20 ml) and refluxed on a steam bath for 7 hrs. The solid that separated on cooling was collected and crystallised from ethanol. Additional amount of the compound was obtained by concentrating the mother liquor Table 1.

Ethyl 2-[(4-phenylthiazolyl) amino]-4, 5-dimethyl-3-thiophenecarboxylate (V) :

A mixture of I (1.99 g; 0.01 mole) and 2-chloro-4-phenylthiazole (IV, 1.95 g; 0.01 mole) was heated on a steam bath for 2 hrs. The hard mass formed was triturated with ethanol (3 ml) and basified with aq. sodium carbonate (10%). The product that separated was crystallised from ethanol as brown needles m.p. 138°, yield 1.97 g (55%). Found : N, 7.64; C₁₈H₁₈N₂O₂S₂ requires N, 7.82%.

6, 7-Dimethyl-3-phenyl-5H-thiazolo [3, 2-a] thieno [2, 3-d] pyrimidine-5-one (VI) :

Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed through an ethanolic solution of V (1.1 g; 0.003 mole in 15 ml). It was refluxed for 4 hrs. Ethanol was removed by distillation and the residue was treated with aq. sodium carbonate (5%). The product which separated was crystallised from ethanol as yellow needles m.p. 230°; yield 0.8 g (83%). Found : C, 61.66; H, 3.80; C₁₆H₁₂N₂OS₂ requires C, 61.54; H, 3.85%.

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Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of N-(substituted Benzylidene)-*p*-(2-Benzimidazolyl)phenoxyacetyl Hydrazides

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BENZIMIDAZOLES have been associated with antiviral¹, antifungal², antibacterial³, insecticidal⁴ and other biological properties⁵. A large number of hydrazides and hydrazones have been reported to possess bactericidal properties⁶⁻⁸. Keeping these observation in mind, a new ester, its hydrazide and hydrazones all containing a benzimidazole moiety have been synthesised to study if the products could display any biological properties.

2-(*p*-Hydroxyphenyl) benzimidazole (Scheme I) was prepared according to reported method^{9,10}. Ethyl-*p*-(2-benzimidazolyl)phenoxy acetate (II) was synthesised by the reaction of I and ethylchloroacetate. Hydrazinolysis of the ester(II) in absolute alcohol gave *p*-(2-

benzimidazolyl) phenoxy acetylhydrazide (III). Synthesis of the *N*-(substituted benzylidene)-*p*-(2-benzimidazolyl) phenoxyacetyl hydrazide (IVa; 1, Table 1) was carried out by refluxing a mixture of hydrazide (III) with aromatic aldehyde/ketone in ethanol in presence of 2-3 drops of glacial acetic acid. Structure of the compounds synthesised were confirmed by their characteristic IR spectra and analytical data.

Scheme I

Scheme II and III

Scheme IV

Biological Screening Results :

(a) *Antibacterial activity* : The method by Varma and Nobles¹¹ was employed for the determination of the antibacterial activity of the compounds IV against *B. subtilis* and *S. typhi* maintained at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. The data is incorporated in Table 1 from which it is generally inferred that association of the -OCH₃ group in these molecules could enhance the activity.

(b) *Antifungal activity* : Compounds no. 3, 7 and 10 of Table 1 were tested for their antifungal activity by following the reported¹² method against two strains of fungus viz. *Fusarium moniliforme* and *Colletotrichum falcatum* Went. All the three compounds were found to be moderately active at the concentration of 1:1,000 against both the fungi.

(c) *Antiamoebic activity* : Compounds no. 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 of Table 1 were also screened for their antiamoebic activity *in vitro* against *E. histolytica* by the method of Das¹³. None of the compounds displayed any activity.

Experimental

The melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137G spectrophotometer in KBr. NMR spectrum was recorded on Varian A-90D spectrophotometer in DMSO D-6 (τ).

Ethyl-p-(2-benzimidazolyl) phenoxyacetate (II) : 2-(*p*-Hydroxyphenyl)benzimidazole (21.0 g, 0.1 mole) and redistilled ethyl chloroacetate (12.25 g, 0.1 mole) in dry acetone were refluxed for 18 hrs in presence of

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA AND ANTIBACTERIAL SCREENING DATA OF SCHIFF'S BASES

Compound Nos.	Aldehyde/ ketone used	m.p. °C	Antibacterial activity against	
			<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>
1. IV _a	Anisaldehyde	175	—	—
2. IV _b	Vanillin	173	+++	++
3. IV _c	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	250	—	—
4. IV _d	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	233	—	++
5. IV _e	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	280	++	++
6. IV _f	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	270	++	—
7. IV _g	<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	220	—	—
8. IV _h	2,3'-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde	288	+++	++
9. IV _i	<i>p</i> -(Dimethylamino)benzaldehyde	188	++	—
10. IV _j	<i>p</i> -Acetamidobenzaldehyde	190	—	—
11. IV _k	Acetophenone	252	—	++
12. IV _l	Propiophenone	152	—	++
	Streptomycin		++++	++++

% N found within ± 0.4 of the calculated values; Yields varied from 60-80 %; Compounds recrystallised from suitable solvents

IR^{*}, (μ) 2.9 (NH), 5.95 (C=O), 6.2 (C=N); NMR^{*}, (τ) 6.97 singlet (CH₂, 6-protons), 5.37 singlet (CH₂, 2 protons), 4.69 singlet (CONH, 1 proton), 3.80 singlet (CH=N, 1 proton), 2.15-3.27 multiplet (Aromatic and Ar-NH-13 protons).

— = no inhibition, + = 6-8 mm; ++ = 9-14 mm; +++ = 15-20 mm and ++++ = more than 20 mm inhibition.

anhydrous potassium carbonate (20.7 g, 0.15 mole). The reaction mixture was filtered and the ester was recovered by evaporating the solvent. It was recrystallised from ethanol; m.p. 215°, yield 80%. Analysis : Found : N, 8.95; H, 5.82; C, 68.50%. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆N₂O₈ : N, 9.45; H, 5.40; C, 68.91%. IR (μ) 5.75 (C=O), 6.3 (C=N).

p-(2-Benzimidazolyl)phenoxyacetyl hydrazide(III) : Ester (II) (2.96 g, 0.01 mole) and hydrazine hydrate (1 ml, 0.02 mole) in absolute alcohol (50 ml) were refluxed for 12 hrs. Excess solvent was removed and the solid obtained on cooling was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol; m.p. 224°, yield 70%. Analysis : N% ; Found : 20.25. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₄N₄O₂ ; 19.85. IR (μ) 3.0 (NH), 5.95 (C=O amide), 6.2 (C=N).

N-(Substituted benzylidene)-*p*-(2-benzimidazolyl) phenoxyacetyl hydrazide (IVa ; 1, Table 1) : Equimolar quantities of the hydrazide (III) and the aldehyde or ketone in ethanol containing 2 drops of glacial acetic acid were refluxed for 4 hrs. The solid, which separated on cooling, was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

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Synthesis and Amoebicidal Activity of Some New N-(2-Nitro 4, 5-Dimethoxy Benzoyl) Glycine Hydrazones.

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A number of *o*-dimethoxy substituted derivatives¹⁻⁵ are reported to possess high amoebicidal activity comparable to that of emetine against *E. histolytica*. It is believed that emetine undergoes some degradation in the system and the *o*-dimethoxy nucleus is the essential part of the degradation products⁶⁻⁸. Recently a large number of hydrazones⁹⁻¹¹ have shown significant amoebicidal activity. Moreover, the amoebicidal activity of compounds containing -CONH- group in halo acetamides¹²⁻¹⁴, has long been known. These observations led us to synthesise some new N-(2-nitro 4, 5-dimethoxy benzoyl) glycine hydrazones and evaluate their amoebicidal activity.

Experimental

The title compounds were synthesised according to the route outlined below.

Ethyl ester of glycine¹⁵ and N-(2-nitro-4,5-dimethoxy benzoyl) glycine ester¹⁶ were prepared according to reported methods. Melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected. Compounds were routinely checked for their homogeneity by tlc on silica gel G.

(a) *N*-(2-nitro-4,5-dimethoxy benzoyl) glycine hydrazone: A mixture of *N*-(2-nitro-4,5-dimethoxy benzoyl) glycine ethyl ester (0.01 mole) and hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mole) was refluxed in absolute ethanol (100 ml) for 8 hrs. The excess solvent was distilled off, the residue cooled, filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. m.p. 180° (N% for C₁₁H₁₄N₄O₆: Found 18.38, Calcd. 18.79).

(b) *N*-(2-nitro-4,5-dimethoxy benzoyl) glycine hydrazones: *N*-(2-nitro-4,5-dimethoxy benzoyl) glycine hydrazone (0.001 mole) was condensed with an appropriate substituted aldehyde or ketone (0.001 mole) by refluxing a mixture of their ethanolic solution for 4 hrs. The desired hydrazones obtained on concentration and cooling were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

The pertinent data of the compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1.

Amoebicidal activity: All the compounds (Table 1) were tested for their amoebicidal activity by the following methods.

The test compound was dissolved in dimethyl formamide. The solution was diluted with water and sterilised by autoclaving at 15 lb per sq. inch pressure for 15 minutes. Thermolabile compounds were tested as such but Penicillin in 1000 and Streptomycin in 1000 µg/ml were added to the media. Tests were conducted at pH between 6.7 to 7.0.

Axenic *E. histolytica* (strain 200: NIH) was maintained in modified IPS-1 medium containing 0.2% cystine in screw capped tubes (16×122 mm). 10,000 amoebae/ml of the medium as determined by Haemo-

**Part of this work will be included in the Ph.D. thesis of Rashmi Srivastava.